

NFDI4Earth

Milestone MS3.2.1

NFDI4Earth Label Status Report

Jonas Grieb ,
Stephan Frickenhaus

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Executive summary

The NFDI4Earth Label is being implemented as a tool to support the harmonisation process of data infrastructures in the Earth System Sciences (ESS) towards a FAIR ecosystem of services for NFDI4Earth. This milestone report gives an overview of the current status of the NFDI4Earth Label which has primarily focused on assessing the technical interoperability of repositories. The interoperability is assessed in a workflow relying on information about a repository that can be retrieved from re3data¹ and an automated FAIRness assessment based on the F-UJI² tool. For this, a set of metrics has been defined and put up for discussion, which are being described in this document. Finally, an outlook on the envisioned further development of NFDI4Earth will be given, which includes implementing and testing the current workflow as well as embedding the interoperability assessment in a broader assessment approach.

¹ re3data.org - Registry of Research Data Repositories. <https://doi.org/10.17616/R3D> last accessed: 2023-12-19

² Devaraju, Anusuriya and Huber, Robert (2021) "An automated solution for measuring the progress toward FAIR research data" *Patterns* 2(11). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2021.100370>

CRediT

JG: Writing – original draft

TS: Writing – original draft

SF: Writing – review & editing

RG: Writing – original draft

CW: Writing – review & editing

Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
CTS	Core Trust Seal, https://www.coretrustseal.org/
ESS	Earth System Science
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GUID	Globally Unique Identifier
GUPID	Globally Unique Persistent Identifier
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OGC CSW	Open Geospatial Consortium Catalog Service for the Web
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID, https://orcid.org/
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDA MSC	Research Data Alliance Metadata Standards Catalog
ROR	Research Organization Registry, https://ror.org/
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

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1. Introduction

Harmonisation of research data-related services in the ESS is one of the key objectives of the NFDI4Earth (Bernard *et al.*, 2021). As a tool to support this harmonisation process, we develop the NFDI4Earth Label which provides a framework to assess the FAIRness of data infrastructures, including their interoperability and trustworthiness. This framework can also be considered a quality assessment with a specific focus on the technical interoperability of infrastructures. Thus, it will support the process of improving interoperability of these infrastructures by (1) providing specific metrics to assess the interoperability of the infrastructure within the NFDI4Earth ecosystem of services, and (2) recommending actions to close the identified gaps.

In a more integrated ecosystem of data infrastructures, these infrastructures form a single knowledge space, in which a common interoperability framework involving a set of metadata exchange protocols and metadata schemas is used.

The NFDI4Earth Label specifically targets infrastructures that can be referred to as “data portals” in a broader sense, including both data repositories (institutional and domain-specific) and metadata aggregators. The label is developed in an iterative fashion. Since interoperability has been identified as an important aspect, in the initial version the Label is focused on the technical interoperability of repositories (but with the aim to e.g. expand the focus to other aspects in the future).

The FAIRness assessment of individual data resources has been a subject of study for several years, in the course of which several tools (e.g., F-UJI, FAIRassist³, FAIR-Checker⁴) have emerged in attempts to define concrete metrics based on the (rather abstract) FAIR principles by Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016. However, the assessment of individual data repositories, or even more generally, services, has only recently become the focus of study. d’Aquin *et al.* (2023) make the case that the traditional categories findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability are not sufficient to represent the social context behind research data repositories, and therefore extended the four categories of the FAIR principles with three more principles: engagement, social connections and trust. Especially in the last principle, trust, d’Aquin *et al.* introduce aspects which are also relevant to the NFDI4Earth Label, like quality-assurance and long-term preservation mechanisms. In the same paper the authors also introduce a set of metrics in the form of a questionnaire to assess whether a system complies with these principles. However, the approach of d’Aquin *et al.* is oriented towards assessing a concrete software system which

³ <https://fairassist.org>

⁴ <https://fair-checker.france-bioinformatique.fr/>

can be used to run a data repository (e.g., CKAN⁵ or INVENIO⁶). In contrast, the goal of the NFDI4Earth Label is to assess existing research data repositories in the community, many of which run based on custom software solutions. Therefore, the approach of d'Aquin et al. is not directly applicable as a foundation for the NFDI4Earth Label.

Other studies focus on the assessment of the individual research artefacts in data repositories (i.e., the hosted datasets) and aggregate the results of the individual assessments to generate an overall FAIRness score for a repository (e.g., European Commission 2022, Preuß *et al.* 2023). This raises the question whether the NFDI4Earth Label intends to assess the FAIRness of a repository as a digital resource itself (the approach of d'Aquin *et al.*, 2023), or whether it aims to assess how FAIR the datasets are that are stored in it. In the context of the NFDI4Earth Label, both aspects are relevant and will be assessed. Using the aggregated FAIRness score of the datasets in a repository as a proxy for the overall FAIRness score for the repository generally seems to be a viable approach, even though it requires placing a certain network load on the repository during the assessment.

Additionally we aim to make use of re3data as a source of information on the repository itself. By using re3data, we are basing the Label on an established community infrastructure where information on a large number of ESS repositories is already stored and curated (updated) by the service providers. Before starting an assessment, we intend to ask repository providers to check and update the information on their repository at re3data. Thus, the information in re3data can be considered to result from a self assessment.

In summary, the NFDI4Earth Label is planned to be awarded based on a combination of information from (1) re3data and (2) an automated interoperability assessment carried out via a FAIR assessment tool. The Label will be visualised in the form of a digital badge which the service providers can add to their website or other service registries.

With the development of the NFDI4Earth Label we therefore plan to achieve two objectives:

1. Provide an indicator for users who search for interoperable and sustainable ESS data repositories.
2. Provide guidance for service providers on how to improve interoperability in case their repository does not yet fulfil all assessed metrics.

The NFDI4Earth Label aims to be complementary to and leverage existing certifications for data repositories, like the Core Trust Seal (CTS)⁷ or the nestor seal⁸. However, in contrast

⁵ <https://ckan.org/>

⁶ <https://inveniosoftware.org/products/rdm/>

⁷ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

⁸ <https://www.langzeitarchivierung.de/Webs/nestor>

to these certifications, the NFDI4Earth Label's evaluation workflow will follow a more light-weight approach, which is based on a self-evaluation process with an automatised, ESS-specific interoperability assessment.

2. Interoperability assessment

With the specific goal of the harmonisation of the research data infrastructures in mind, a first set of metrics was defined which focus on the assessment of the technical interoperability of a repository. Therefore, some general metrics are assessed (e.g., whether a repository assigns persistent identifiers (PIDs)) and also some more specific metrics which require the support of some standards to allow for the integration into the envisioned ecosystem of services. The metrics are derived from the FAIRsFAIR data object assessment metrics (Devajaru *et al.* 2022). These focus primarily on datasets but also take into account the FAIR-enabling repository in which a dataset is embedded. For the NFDI4Earth Label, we focus exclusively on the repository.

The principal source of information used to assess the NFDI4Earth Label interoperability metrics on a specific repository is re3data. From re3data, information like supported metadata standards, provided API endpoints and supported PID systems are retrieved and evaluated against a normative set of requirements for the NFDI4Earth infrastructure. However, not all questions required to evaluate the FAIRness of an infrastructure can be answered based on the information that is currently available in re3data. For instance, re3data does not provide information that regard the direct content of the metadata of individual datasets served by the repository, as for example whether the metadata contains descriptive core elements (comparable FAIRsFAIR metric FsF-F2-01M or FAIR principle F2), or whether provenance information is provided (see FsF-R1.2-01M or FAIR principle R1.2). To obtain this additional information, we make use of the F-UJI tool to run an automated FAIR assessment on a randomly sampled subset of datasets in a repository and use the aggregated result as a proxy to assess these metrics on the level of the repository. However, this assessment process can only be initiated after the retrieval of the re3data record for a repository, because it requires information like the URL of a harvestable API endpoint of the repository (if any), which we obtain from the re3data record. Currently the F-UJI assessment is only initiated when the re3data record of a repository states that an API endpoint according to the OAI-PMH protocol⁹ is available and the given endpoint provides a valid response. In summary, the assessment process will include the following steps:

1. Retrieve the re3data record for the (required)
2. Assessment of re3data information (required)

⁹ <https://www.openarchives.org/OAI/openarchivesprotocol.html>

3. F-UJI assessment (optional)

2.1. Integration and Harmonisation Metrics

At the moment, 19 different integration and harmonisation metrics have been defined, out of which 15 can already be evaluated automatically for the NFDI4Earth Label assessment. The remaining four metrics require either further discussion or additional technical implementation. The metrics can be categorised into four different categories: findability-enablement, accessibility-enablement, interoperability-enablement and reusability-enablement. Two additional metrics are outside of these categories, because they assess the state of registration of the repository in re3data itself.

2.1.1. Findability-enablement

To enable findability¹⁰ of its data, a repository must assign persistent identifiers and provide descriptive metadata records for the contained datasets (aligning with FAIR principles F2 and F3).

2.1.2. Accessibility-enablement

To enable accessibility a repository must provide its metadata (and data) via a machine-readable protocol. For the NFDI4Earth Label, we assess not only whether any type of API is available, but also check in a separate metric whether one of the available APIs conforms to a standardised metadata harvesting protocol. Here we define OAI-PMH (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting) or OGC-CSW (the Catalogue Service for the Web standard, as defined by the Open Geospatial Consortium) as protocols which should be supported by an ESS repository in order to be part of the ecosystem of services.

2.1.3. Interoperability-enablement

To enable interoperability especially with respect to a semantic integration within the NFDI4Earth, a repository must provide the metadata of datasets according to a community defined metadata standard. Here we assess the metadata standards listed in the re3data record and perform an automatic FAIR assessment of a sample of the datasets in a repository via the F-UJI tool (if possible). We additionally define a specific set of metadata schemas which

¹⁰ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* **3**, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

must be supported so that the metadata contained in a repository can be integrated into the envisioned semantic knowledge space. Currently this list includes the Datacite Metadata Schema¹¹, GeoDCAT-AP¹² and the ISO 19115 standard¹³, as these are standards well-known in the Earth System Sciences (Grieb et al, 2023).

2.1.4. Reusability-enablement

To enable reusability of the data and metadata contained in a repository, the datasets' metadata should provide provenance and license information. This is assessed via applying the F-UJI assessment tool on a sample of datasets in a repository, if possible.

A list with the first set of provisional interoperability metrics for the NFDI4Earth Label assessment can be found in Appendix 1. However, it is to be noted that the development process of the NFDI4Earth Label is ongoing, and therefore all metrics are still under discussion.

2.2. Implementation and rating

A prototypical implementation, which assesses the metrics described above and stores the result in a JSON object is being developed in the form of a Python script¹⁴. The script is integrated with the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub (Degbelo *et al.* 2022) in the way that it retrieves structured metadata about NFDI4Earth repositories, which has been harvested from re3data, directly from the Knowledge Hub's SPARQL endpoint, and storing of the assessment results in the Knowledge Hub is in progress. At the moment, the assessment result consists of a plain list of the individual metrics and whether each metric was fulfilled or not, together with a reason statement. A weighting of individual metrics is not implemented yet. Open tasks include the definition of minimum requirements (apart from the requirement to have a re3data record) for obtaining the NFDI4Earth Label, and a weighting of metrics as part of a method to aggregate the individual metrics into an overall (categorised) Label score.

¹¹ <https://schema.datacite.org/>

¹² <https://semiceu.github.io/GeoDCAT-AP/drafts/latest/>

¹³ <https://www.iso.org/standard/53798.html>

¹⁴ <https://git.rwth-aachen.de/nfdi4earth/knowledgehub/nfdi4earth-label>

3. Report on the first workshop on October 18th, 2023

On the 18th of October, 2023, the NFDI4Earth Label working group conducted the first virtual workshop with the aim to discuss first ideas regarding the NFDI4Earth Label Concept and collect feedback from the community. Since the Label itself is still in a very early development phase, the workshop was announced internally within the NFDI4Earth consortium and was targeted at a selection of repository providers which are part of the consortium. The workshop was attended by 25 participants, among these were representatives of 12 different ESS repositories, and the workshop lasted about hours. This workshop was the first in a series of events that will be held during the label development process. Further discussions with the community, including repository providers, are planned at events like the next meeting in Frankfurt at the beginning of March, and at the NFDI4Earth plenary.

Table 2: List of repository providers which were represented in the workshop

Infrastructure Name	Website
Bayerisches Hauptstaatsarchiv	iv https://www.gda.bayern.de/hauptstaatsarchiv/
BGR Geoportal	https://geoportal.bgr.de
DWD Global Information and Service Center (GISC)	https://gisc.dwd.de
Edaphobase	https://portal.edaphobase.org/
GeoROC Database	https://georoc.eu
GEOFON	https://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/
GFZ Data Services	https://dataservices.gfz-potsdam.de
Scientific Drilling Databases	e https://dataservices.gfz-potsdam.de/portal/?fq=datacentre/_symbol:DOIDB.SDDB
Integrated Climate Data Center	ter https://www.cen.uni-hamburg.de/en/icdc.html
OceanRep GEOMAR Repository	https://oceanrep.geomar.de/
PANGAEA	https://www.pangaea.de/
World Data Center for Climate	te https://www.wdc-climate.de

At the beginning, Javier Quinteros gave a keynote speech on the experiences he and his team have had using the F-UJI tool in GEOFON¹⁵. As part of GEOFON, Javier was heavily involved in the development of F-UJI through intensive testing and feedback loops.

Afterwards, Jonas Grieb presented the current status of work on the Label on behalf of the NFDI4Earth Label process team.

In the ensuing discussion, different concerns and suggestions were voiced. The main topics were:

- Clarification of the project goals

¹⁵ <https://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de>

The main question here was whether the Label is supposed to be an assessment, or a formal certification like CTS, and how it differs from existing approaches. It became clear that the former is the case, meaning the NFDI4Earth Label is supposed to be an assessment of the technical capabilities and standards supported by ESS repositories. The goal is to be able to measure technical interoperability over time and identify opportunities for improvement.

- Governance

If the Label is a certification or something that is publicly displayed in the name of NFDI4Earth, who is responsible for it, and who defines which aspects of a repository are judged by which criteria? It was agreed that this aspect requires more clarification, and that technical aspects that can be judged automatically by existing tools like F-UJI are the focus of the NFDI4Earth Label.

- Visualisation and comparability of different repositories

The presentation of the first draft of the Label visualisation included three Label levels represented by colours (bronze, silver, gold). It was criticised that the colours imply a hierarchy, and that due to substantial differences between repositories in age, community size, funding and other aspects, comparing repositories via a hierarchical representation may not be practical.

These points were further discussed in subsequent meetings of the NFDI4Earth Label team, and served as valuable pointers for the evolution of the project.

4. Outlook

The presented report on the current status of the NFDI4Earth Label reflects the current state of discussion of the NFDI4Earth Label working group. The principal focus of the NFDI4Earth Label was and will be the interoperability assessment of repositories in the Earth System Sciences. However, as it became clear during the workshop and also in parallel discussions within the NFDI4Earth consortium, this should not be the only category of quality criteria that the Label assesses. In order to support a sustainable ecosystem of ESS services, other quality criteria such as sustainable funding or long-term archiving strategies are also important and should be considered in the Label assessment. In this context, the Label could also consider whether a repository achieved a certification like the CTS or Nestor which can serve as an indication that some of these criteria have been fulfilled.

We will design a concept that takes up on the given criticism, embedding the implemented interoperability assessment in a broader approach which also assesses the sustainability of an infrastructure. For this, an additional self-assessment part will be included in the assessment workflow, since sustainability is harder to define and measure technically, and is therefore less suitable for an automated assessment. This concept will be aligned with related activities like the NFDI4Earth FAIRness and Openness Commitment currently under discussion. Along with this updated concept we will implement a prototype that handles the whole workflow required to obtain the NFDI4Earth Label. This includes a user interface which allows the representative of a data infrastructure to request the NFDI4Earth Label assessment and to input additional information which we cannot retrieve from re3data at the moment.

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A. Appendix 1

Provisional interoperability metrics which the NFDI4Earth Label could assess (currently under discussion). GUID, Globally Unique Identifier; GUUID, Globally Unique Persistent Identifier; API, Application Programming Interface; RDA MSC, Research Data Alliance Metadata Standards Catalog; ROR, Research Organization Registry; ORCID, Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier; OAI-PMH, Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting; OGC CSW, Open Geospatial Consortium Catalog Service for the Web.

Metric-Identifier	Description	Source	Status	Related FAIR principle
n4e-re3dataRegistered	The repository must be registered at re3data.	re3data	Available	
n4e-re3dataUpToDate	The re3data record is up-to-date.	re3data + custom processing	Needs implementation	
n4e-assignsUniquelds	The repository assigns GUIDs.	re3data	Available	F1: (Meta)data is assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers.
n4e-assignsPersistentIds	The repository assigns GUPIDs.	re3data	Available	F1: (Meta)data is assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers.
n4e-hasDescriptiveMetadata	Metadata of records include descriptive core elements.	F-UJI (FsF-F2-01M)	Available	F2: Data is described with rich metadata.
n4e-hasDescriptiveMetadataESS	Metadata of datasets includes additionally spatiotemporal core elements.	F-UJI + custom	Needs implementation	F2: Data is described with rich metadata.
n4e-metadataIncludesIdentifier	Metadata of records includes the identifier of the data it describes.	F-UJI (FsF-F3-01M)	Available	F3: Metadata clearly and explicitly includes the identifier of the data it describes.
n4e-providesAnyAPI	The repository provides any type of API to access the metadata.	re3data	Available	A1: (Meta)data is retrievable by its identifier using a standardized communication protocol.
n4e-providesHarvestableAPI	The API can be harvested into the NFDI4Earth because it conforms to OAI-PMH or OGC CSW.	re3data	Available	A1: (Meta)data is retrievable by its identifier using a standardized communication protocol.
n4e-metadataRepresentation	Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.	F-UJI (FsF-I1-01M)	Available	I1: (Meta)data uses a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
n4e-semanticResources	Metadata uses semantic resources.	F-UJI (FsF-I1-02M)	Available	I2: (Meta)data uses vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.
n4e-metadataLinks	Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities.	F-UJI (FsF-I3-01M)	Available	I3: (Meta)data includes qualified references to other (meta)data.
n4e-usesCommonIdentifierSchemes	Metadata referencing persons or organizations should include according identifiers, like ORCID and ROR.	custom processing	Needs implementation	I3: (Meta)data includes qualified references to other (meta)data.
n4e-supportsCrossDomainStandard	The repository supports at least one cross-domain metadata standard.	re3data + RDA MSC	Available	F4: (Meta)data is registered or indexed in a searchable resource.
n4e-supportsSpecificNFDI4EarthStandard	The data repository be integrated into the NFDI4Earth because it supports at least one of: GeoDCAT, ISO19115, Datacite	re3data	Available	R1.3. (Meta)data meets domain-relevant community standards.
n4e-supportsMetadataStandardsByScientificDomain	The repository additionally supports at least one domain-specific metadata standard.	re3data + RDA MSC	Needs further discussion	R1.3. (Meta)data meets domain-relevant community standards.
n4e-specifiesContent	Metadata specifies the content of the data: it includes the type of the object and the technical properties of its data file such as format, size, observed or measured variables.	F-UJI (FsF-R1-01MD)	Available	R1: (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.
n4e-includesLicense	Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.	F-UJI (FsF-R1.1-01M)	Available	R1.1. (Meta)data is released with a clear and accessible data usage license.
n4e-includesProvenance	Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.	F-UJI (FsF-R1.2-01M)	Available	R1.2. (Meta)data is associated with detailed provenance.